

Synthesis and PMR Spectral Analysis of Some N-Chloropiperidin-4-ones and N-Chloroazabicyclo[3.3.1]nonan-9-ones

K. GANAPATHY and B. VIJAYAN

Department of Chemistry, Annamalai University, Annamalainagar-608 002

Manuscript received 17 March 1982, revised 15 March 1983, accepted 20 May 1983

Various substituted N-chloropiperidin-4-ones and N-chloroazabicyclo[3.3.1]nonan-9-ones have been prepared and they are found to be good oxidising agents. PMR spectra of the substituted N-chloropiperidin-4-ones reveal that they exist in chair conformation. The bicyclic compounds except N,N'-dichloro-2,4,6,8-tetraphenyl-3,7-diazabicyclo[3.3.1]nonan-9-one exist in twin-chair conformation while the latter compound exists in chair-boat conformation. In the case of substituted N-chloropiperidin-4-ones the equatorial proton absorbs at higher field than the axial proton and the equatorial methyl protons absorb at higher field than the axial methyl protons. The equatorial methyl group at C₂ or C₆ shields the vicinal axial hydrogens at C₃ or C₅ and the axial methyl group at C₂ deshields the axial proton at C₃. Such an effect is also observed in the case of the bicyclic compounds.

THE chemistry of N-chloro compounds is very fascinating and has received considerable attention through the years, resulting in substantial advances both in the synthetic^{1,2} and mechanistic categories³. In the present paper a series of new remarkable oxidants namely N-chloropiperidin-4-ones and N-chloroazabicyclo[3.3.1]nonan-9-ones are reported.

Results and Discussion

Noller and Baliah⁴ developed a satisfactory procedure for the synthesis of 2,6-diarylpiperidin-4-ones. The various substituted 2,6-diarylpiperidin-4-

ones, prepared by condensing different aliphatic ketones and aromatic aldehydes with ammonium acetate yield on chlorination the N-chloro-2,6-diarylpiperidin-4-ones (I).

Azabicyclic compounds⁵ obtained by condensing cyclic ketones with ammonium acetate and aromatic aldehydes, yield the N-chloroazabicyclo[3.3.1]nonan-9-ones (II) on chlorination. The N-chloro compounds have been characterised by ir and nmr spectral analysis. Their analytical data are listed in Table 1.

- Ar = Phenyl
 Ia - R₁, R₃, R₂, R₄ = H
 Ib - R₁ = CH₃; R₂, R₃, R₄ = H
 Ic - R₁ = C₂H₅; R₂, R₃, R₄ = H
 Id - R₁ = CH(CH₃)₂; R₂, R₃, R₄ = H
 Ie - R₁ = (CH₂)₃-CH₃; R₂, R₃, R₄ = H
 If - R₁, R₂ = CH₃; R₃, R₄ = H
 Ig - R₁, R₂ = CH₃; R₃, R₄ = H
 Ih - R₁, R₂ = C₂H₅; R₃, R₄ = H
 Ar = *o*-Chlorophenyl
 Ii - R₁ = CH₃; R₂, R₃, R₄ = H
 X = CH₃
 IIa - Ar₁ = Ph; Ar₂ = H; R = H
 IIb - Ar₁ = Ph; Ar₂ = H; R = CH₃
 IIc - Ar₁ = *o*-Cl-C₆H₄; Ar₂ = H; R = H
 X = N-Cl
 IId - Ar₁ = Ph; Ar₂ = Ph; R = H

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE N-CHLOROCOMPOUNDS

Com- pound	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)	
			C	H
Ia	137-38	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClNO	71.02 (71.45)	5.23 (5.60)
Ib	144-45	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ClNO	72.25 (72.12)	6.27 (6.01)
Ic	131-32	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ ClNO	72.50 (72.72)	6.69 (6.38)
Id	124-25	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ ClNO	73.43 (73.28)	6.78 (6.72)
Ie	131-32	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ ClNO	73.54 (73.79)	6.89 (7.02)
If	143-44	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ ClNO	72.72 (72.72)	6.50 (6.38)
Ig	138-39	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ ClNO	72.97 (72.72)	6.95 (6.38)
Ih	141-42	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ ClNO	79.32 (79.54)	5.62 (5.48)
Ii	162-63	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ NO	58.32 (58.62)	4.54 (4.34)
IIa	128-29	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ ClNO	73.53 (73.73)	6.56 (6.14)
IIb	126-27	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ ClNO	74.08 (74.23)	6.54 (6.48)
IIc	145-46	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ NO	61.04 (60.81)	4.41 (4.56)
IId	143-44	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O	72.08 (72.51)	5.31 (5.06)

TABLE 2—PMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF THE N-CHLORO-2,6-DIPHENYLPIPERIDIN-4-ONES*

Compound	H-2	H-6	H-2,6	H-3	H-5	H-3,5	CH ₃ -30r5
Ia	3 —	—	4.2 (2-q)	—	—	2.8 (2-q) 2.5 (2-q)	—
Ib	3.9 (1-d)	4.3 (1-q)	—	—	—	2.6-3.5 (3-m)	0.9 (3-d)
Ig	—	—	3.8 (2-d)	—	—	2.9 (2-d)	0.9 (6-d)
Ij	4.0 (1-s)	4.2 (1-q)	—	—	3.2 (1-q) 2.6 (1-q)	—	1.4 (3-s), 1.0 (3-s)

* Phenyl protons absorb at 7.3–7.4 δ .

The N-chloro compounds are found to be good oxidising agents. They can also be used as primary standards since they are stable crystalline solids and are able to liberate iodine quantitatively and instantaneously from acidified iodide solution even in very low concentrations.

With a view of understanding the preferred conformations of the title compounds the pmr spectra of some selected compounds were recorded and analysed (Table 2).

N-Chloro-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one (Ia): Ouellette *et al*⁶ studied the conformation of isopropyl benzene and proposed that the methine proton appearing at 2.8 δ is coplanar with the phenyl ring. Here also, the benzylic protons of the N-chloro compound (Ia) absorb at down field. This shows that the two phenyl rings are coplanar with benzylic protons. When the spectrum is re-recorded irradiating at 2.5 δ , the benzylic proton signal is obtained as a doublet with a coupling constant of 10 Hz. It shows clearly that the compound exists in chair conformation with axial benzylic protons and equatorial phenyl groups at C₃ and C₆.

The methylene protons at C₃ and C₅ give two types of peaks, one centered at 2.8 δ and the other at 2.5 δ . It is evident from the decoupling study that the peak with a greater band-width at 2.8 δ is due to the axial protons and the other at 2.5 δ is due to the equatorial protons. It is interesting to note that contrary to the usual behaviour, the equatorial protons absorb at up field instead of the axial protons.

N-Chloro-3-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one (Ib): The benzylic proton at 3.9 δ appears as a doublet with a coupling constant of 10 Hz. The coupling constant shows that the compound exists in chair conformation. The peaks due to the methine and methylene protons at C₃ and C₅, respectively are mingled and form a broad multiplet from 2.6 to 3.5 δ . It is interesting to note that the peaks due to

the benzylic protons at C₃ and C₆ are well separated and the one at C₂ occurs at higher field. The shielding experienced by the axial proton at C₂ may be due to the equatorial methyl group at C₃. A similar effect was observed by Booth⁷ in the case of substituted cyclohexanes.

N-Chloro-3,5-dimethyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one (Ic): The signals of the benzylic protons at C₃ and C₆ are well separated. The proton at C₃ is shielded by the equatorial methyl group at C₅. But the shielding is not as effective as in the case of compounds (Ib) and (Id). It may be due to the axial methyl group at C₃ which deshields the axial proton at C₂ to a certain extent. The two peaks due to the methylene protons at C₅ occur at 3.2 and 2.6 δ . The one-proton peak at 3.2 δ is assigned to the axial proton at C₅. The signal of equatorial proton at C₅ appears at 2.6 δ which is assigned from the band-width of the peaks. Here also the equatorial proton absorbs at higher field than the axial proton. Two 3-proton singlet peaks are observed at 1.4 and 1.0 δ . The peak observed at 1.0 δ may be due to the equatorial methyl group since in the case of the compound (II) also the equatorial methyl protons absorb at 0.9 δ . The other peak at 1.4 δ is assigned to the axial methyl protons. It is to be noted that equatorial methyl protons absorb at higher field than the axial methyl protons.

PMR spectra of some of the bicyclic compounds are recorded in Table 3. Kinetic measurements⁸ with these bicyclic compounds suggest that all of them, except N-N'-dichloro-2,4,5,8-tetraphenyl-3,7-diazabicyclo[3.3.1]nonan-9-one (IIId), exist in twin-chair conformation. The latter exists in chair-boat conformation and the pmr spectra of these compounds also support the above fact.

As it is observed in the monocyclic compounds, the methyl group at C₁ in the case of N-chloro-2,4-diphenyl-1-methyl-3-azabicyclo[3.3.1]nonan-9-one (IIb) shields the vicinal axial proton at C₃ and thus

TABLE 3—PMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF THE N-CHLOROAZABICYCLO[3.3.1]NONAN-9-ONES

Compound	Phenyl protons	H-2	H-4	H-2,4	H-1	H-5	H-15	H-6,7,8
IIb*	7.3 (10-m)	4.0 (1-s)	4.5 (1-d)	—	—	2.6 (1-m)	—	2.0–1.5 (6-m)
IIc	7.9 (2-m) 7.3 (6-m)	—	—	5.1 (2-d)	—	—	2.8 (2-m)	1.5–2.0 (6-m)
IIId	7.4 (10-m), 6.9 (6-m), 6.5 (4-m)	—	—	4.5 (2-d)	—	—	2.3 (2-m)	4.7 (2-d)

* Methyl protons absorb at 0.8 δ .

the benzylic proton at C₃ absorbs at higher field than the other benzylic proton at C₄. The benzylic protons of the compound absorb at comparatively down field than the monocyclic benzylic protons. The deshielding of the axial protons at C₂ and C₄ in the bicyclic system may be due to the other carbocyclic ring which is axial at C₁ and C₅. This confirms that the axial methyl or methylene group shields the vicinal axial hydrogen in the case of cyclic compounds that exist in chair conformation. In the pmr spectrum of N-chloro-2,4-bis(*o*-chlorophenyl)-3-azabicyclo[3.3.1]nonan-9-one (IIc), a two-proton multiplet at 7.9 δ and a 6-proton multiplet at 7.3 δ are observed. The highly deshielded two-proton multiplet may be due to the protons in the two phenyl groups at 6' position. In this compound the *o*-chlorophenyl group is oriented in such a way that the chlorine atoms of the phenyl rings are *syn* to C₂ and C₄ axial hydrogens. It is an energetically favourable orientation and is evident from the kinetics of oxidation of cyclohexanone-oxime by this compound⁶. In such orientation the two C₆ protons of the two phenyl groups are oriented *anti* to C₂ and C₄ axial hydrogens (below the piperidone ring) so that it may be more deshielded by the lone pair of the nitrogen of the piperidone ring. The 6-proton peak may be due to the other phenyl protons. The peak at 5.1 δ is due to the benzylic protons which is more deshielded by the electron-withdrawing *o*-chlorophenyl group.

The pmr spectrum of N,N'-dichloro-2,4,6,8-tetraphenyl-3,7-diazabicyclo[3.3.1]nonan-9-one (IIId) shows three peaks at 7.4, 6.9 and 6.5 δ . Kinetic measurements with this compound show that it exists in chair-boat conformation. The 10-proton multiplet at 7.4 δ may be due to the phenyl protons (of the phenyl groups) attached to the piperidone ring which is in chair conformation. Dreding model of the compound shows that 4 protons of the two phenyl groups belonging to the piperidone ring with boat conformation are oriented above the plane of the phenyl groups which are in the other piperidone ring with chair conformation. But the *vice versa* is not possible in such orientation. Therefore the peak at up field (6.5 δ) is due to the four protons. The 6-proton multiplet at 6.9 δ may be due to the other phenyl protons of the piperidone moiety which is in boat conformation.

The two different peaks (at 4.7 and 4.5 δ) due to the benzylic protons are observed in the pmr spectrum. The comparatively more deshielded proton may be the benzylic protons of the piperidone ring in boat conformation and the peak at 4.5 δ

may be due to the benzylic protons of the other ring which is in chair conformation. Dreding model of the compound shows that the benzylic protons in the boat ring are deshielded by the phenyl rings which are in the chair conformation. The 2-proton multiplet at 3.0 δ is due to the bridge-head protons.

Experimental

All melting points recorded are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. PMR spectra were recorded by the spectrometer supplied by Perkin-Elmer (90 MHz).

General procedure for the preparation of N-chloro-piperidin-4-one :

The 2,6-diarylpiperidin-4-one hydrochloride (0.25 mole) prepared by the method of Noller and Baliah⁴ was dissolved in ethanol-water mixture (50-75%). Chlorine gas was passed through the solution for about 15 min. During chlorination the N-chlorinated piperidone was thrown out and more water was added to precipitate completely the N-chlorinated compound. The yield was almost quantitative. It was filtered and washed well with water. The N-chlorinated piperidone was crystallised from ethanol.

Chlorination of the azabicyclic compound was carried out by a similar method dissolving the azabicyclic compound in benzene-ethanol mixture instead of aqueous ethanol. After chlorination the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The chlorinated compound was washed well with ethanol and crystallised from benzene-ethanol mixture.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi for the award of a Junior Fellowship to one of them (B. V.).

References

1. P. GASSMAN, F. HAYDA and J. DYGOS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2739.
2. P. KOVAIC, M. K. LOWERY and K. W. FIELD, *Chem. Rev.*, 1970, 70, 639.
3. S. WAWZONEK and P. J. THELEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2118.
4. C. R. NOLLER and V. BALIAH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3853.
5. V. BALIAH and R. JEYARAMAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 1020.
6. R. J. OUELLETTE, B. K. SINHA, C. STOLFE, C. LEVIN and S. WILLIAMS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 92, 7145.
7. H. BOOTH, *Tetrahedron*, 1966, 615.
8. K. GANAPATHY and B. VIJAYAN, unpublished results.